

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17942415>

MULTIDISCIPLINARY COMPUTER DESIGN TOOLS FOR WIND TURBINE

Pulatov Behzod Mannonovich

Tashkent state technical university after named Islam Karimov,
s. Tashkent Uzbekistan.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada shamol turbinalarini loyihalashda qo'llaniladigan ko'p tarmoqli (aerodinamika, mexanika, elektr va boshqaruv tizimlari) kompyuter modellashtirish vositalarining roli yoritilgan. Shamol energetikasi taraqqiyoti tarixiy misollar orqali ko'rsatilib, zamonaviy turbinalarning konstruktiv xususiyatlari, doimiy va o'zgaruvchan tezlikdagi generator tizimlari hamda quvvatni boshqarish strategiyalari tahlil qilingan.

***Kalit so'zlar:** shamol turbinalari, aerodinamika, boshqaruv tizimlari, DFIG, pitch control, stall control, o'zgaruvchan tezlik, elektr generatorlari, ko'p tarmoqli dizayn.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются многоотраслевые компьютерные инструменты проектирования ветровых турбин, позволяющие одновременно моделировать аэродинамические, механические, электрические и управляющие системы. Приведён исторический обзор развития ветроэнергетики и анализируются современные конструкции турбин, включая машины постоянной и переменной скорости, методы регулирования мощности, а также роль систем управления в повышении эффективности и надёжности работы.

Ключевые слова: ветровая турбина, аэродинамика, системы управления, DFIG, pitch-контроль, stall-контроль, переменная скорость, электрогенераторы, многодисциплинарное проектирование.

ANNOTATION

This paper discusses multidisciplinary computer design tools used for wind turbine development, integrating aerodynamics, mechanical structures, electrical systems, and control engineering. A brief historical review of wind turbine evolution is presented, followed by an analysis of modern turbine configurations, including constant-speed and variable-speed machines, power regulation strategies and the growing importance of control systems in achieving optimal performance.

Keywords: wind turbine, aerodynamics, control systems, DFIG, pitch control, stall control, variable speed, electric generators, multidisciplinary design.

Charles F. Brush is widely credited with designing and erecting the world's first automatically operating wind turbine for electricity generation. The turbine, which was installed in Cleveland, Ohio, in 1887, operated for 20 years with a peak power production of 12 kW (Fig. 1).

Figure1. Charles F. Brush's wind turbine (1887, Cleveland, Ohio), the world's first automatically operating wind turbine for electricity generation.

An automatic control system ensured that the turbine achieved effective action at 6.6 rpm (330 rpm at the dynamo) and that the dc voltage was kept between 70 and 90 Volts. Another remarkable project in early wind energy research was the 1.25-MW wind turbine developed by Palmer Putnam in the U.S. The giant wind turbine, which was 53 m (175 feet) in diameter, was installed in Vermont, Pennsylvania, around 1940 and featured two blades with a hydraulic pitch control system.

Modern wind-driven electricity generators began appearing during the late 1970s. At that time, the average power output of a wind turbine unit was about 50 kW with a blade length of 8 m. Since then, the size of the machines has increased dramatically. Nowadays, the typical values for power output of the modern turbines deployed around the world are about 1.5 to 3.5 MW with blade lengths of more than 40 m for onshore and 60 m for offshore applications. Simultaneously, the cost per kilowatt has decreased significantly, and the efficiency, reliability, and availability of the machines have definitely improved. availability of the machines have definitely improved.

New multidisciplinary computer design tools able to simulate, analyze, and redesign in a concurrent engineering way the aerodynamics, mechanics, and electrical and control systems under several conditions and external scenarios have extended the capability to develop more complex and efficient wind turbines. In this new approach (Fig. 2), the control system designs, and the designers' understanding of the system's dynamics from the control standpoint, are playing a central role in new engineering achievements. Far better than in the old days, when the design of any machine was carried out under a rigid and sequential strategy, starting from the pure aerodynamics and following with the mechanical, the electrical, and finally the control system design, the new tools have opened the door to a more central role for control engineers. The new philosophy brings a concurrent engineering approach, where all the engineering teams work simultaneously to achieve the optimum wind turbine design. This strategy allows the control engineers to interact with designers from the other fields from the

very beginning, discussing and changing the aerodynamics, mechanics, and electrical systems to improve the dynamic behavior, efficiency, reliability, availability, and cost, and finally to design the most appropriate controllers for the machine.

Figure 2. Multidisciplinary computer design tools for wind turbine design

Nowadays, there are essentially two types of wind turbines: constant-speed and variable-speed machines. Until the late nineties, the constant-speed concept dominated the market. Today, it still represents a significant share of the operating wind turbines, but newer requirements have led to the emergence of variable-speed designs.

Three main alternative strategies are used for regulating the amount of power captured by the rotor: passive stall control or fixed pitch, variable pitch control, and active stall control. So far, over the entire range of wind turbine sizes, no one of these strategies has taken the lead over the others. However, as machines get larger and power production increases, the trend is toward pitch control and active stall control.

The configuration of a fixed-speed wind turbine is based on a gearbox and an asynchronous generator, which is usually a squirrel-cage induction generator to reduce costs. The gearbox links the wind turbine shaft with the rotor of a fixed-speed generator, providing the high rotational speed required by the generator.

The generator produces electricity through a direct grid connection, and a set of capacitors is used to compensate reactive power. Due to lack of a frequency converter,

the generator speed is dictated by the grid frequency. One disadvantage of fixed-speed operation is poor aerodynamic efficiency, particularly at partial-load operation. From the electrical system's standpoint, another disadvantage is that this type of operation has a detrimental effect on voltage because asynchronous generators demand reactive power from the grid.

Another alternative to the popular squirrel-cage asynchronous generator is the so-called slip control method, which adjusts the slip changing the synchronous speed the electrical resistance of the rotor, small changes in the rotational speed variation of about 10% above can be compensated for without varying the generator output frequency

Many options have been developed to achieve some degree of speed variation: (1) dual-speed generators with pole switching (the use of a lower speed in low wind conditions improves performance and reduces noise emissions); (2) variable-resistance asynchronous generators for a low range of variable speed; (3) doubly fed induction generators (DFIGs) for a moderate range of variable speed; and finally, (4) direct-drive multipole synchronous generator systems and (5) hybrid systems (combination of multipole generators with small gearboxes), both for a wide range of variable speed

Especially dominant in new markets is the DFIG, also called the wound rotor induction generator. In this machine, the stator windings are directly connected to the grid, while a frequency converter interfaces between the standard wound rotor and the grid. The stator winding connection carries most of the power production, although the frequency converter may carry up to a third of the total power, depending on the operating mode. This configuration allows the machine to control the slip in the generator, and thus the rotor speed can vary moderately, achieving better aerodynamic efficiency. Furthermore, as the converter controls the rotor voltage magnitude and phase angle, partial control of active and reactive power is also possible.

Finally, another approach, which will probably dominate in offshore applications, is the multipole synchronous generator connected to the grid through a power electronic converter that handles the full power production. This concept, also called the direct-drive machine, takes advantage of the wide speed range allowed by the full-

scale frequency converter. The generator can operate at any rotational speed, allowing operation to track the optimal speed for each wind condition. Among the main advantages of this approach are low maintenance costs and high reliability due to omission of the gearbox, improved aerodynamic efficiency, and the ability to assist grid voltage control.

A generic qualitative power curve for a variable-speed pitch-controlled wind turbine is shown in Fig. 3. Four zones and two areas are indicated in the figure [1]. The rated power P_r of the wind turbine (that is the actual power supplied to the grid at wind speed greater than V_r) separates the graph into two main areas. Below rated power, the wind turbine produces only a fraction of its total design power, and therefore an optimization control strategy needs to be performed. Conversely, above rated power, a limitation control strategy is required.

For passive-stall-controlled wind turbines, in which the rotor blades are fixed to the hub at a specific angle, the generator reaction torque regulates rotor speed below rated operation to maximize energy capture. Above a specific wind speed, the geometry of the rotor induces stall. In this manner, the power delivered by the rotor is limited in high wind conditions thanks to a particular design of the blades that provokes loss of efficiency

Figure 3. Power curve of a wind turbine and control zones

In pitch control, the power delivered by the rotor is regulated either by pitching the blades toward the wind to maximize energy capture or by pitching to feather to discard the excess power and ensure that the mechanical limitations are not exceeded. At rated operation, the aim is to maintain power and rotor speed at their rated value. To achieve this, the torque is held constant and the pitch is continually changed following the demands of a closed-loop rotor speed controller that optimizes energy capture and follows wind speed variations. In contrast, below rated operation there is no pitch control; the blade is set to a fine pitch position to yield higher power capture values while the generator torque itself regulates the rotor speed.

Active stall control is a combination of stall and pitch control. It offers the same regulation possibilities as the pitch-regulated turbine but uses the stall properties of the blades. Above rated operation, the control system pitches the blades to induce stall instead of feathering. In this technique, the blades are rotated only by small amounts and less frequently than for pitch control.

REFERENCES

1. E. Hau. Wind Turbines. Fundamentals, Technologies, Application, Economics (2nd ed.). Berlin: Springer, 2006.
2. NREL (National Renewable Energy Laboratory). NWTC Design Codes (FAST), An Aeroelastic Design Code for Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines, 2010.
3. T. Burton, D. Sharpe, N. Jenkins, and E. Bossany. Wind Energy Handbook. London: Wiley, 2001.